

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-179-ADH-1% 05 rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	86	Acq. Method Set:	1% 210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 2 179
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/4/2023 19:58:48 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 21:09:16 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	23.061	215449	8.82	5690
2	24.010	232380	9.52	5677
3	25.605	1008044	41.28	24852
4	28.431	986180	40.38	22988

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-181-ADH-1% 05 RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230308
Vial:	44	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 181
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	35.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 3:44:02 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:20:23 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	23.218	15998	0.34	588
2	24.205	14418	0.30	689
3	25.942	3895	0.08	158
4	28.388	4730311	99.28	105574